

SYNTHESIS OF NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART V.

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Diethylamino and piperidino derivatives of 5-, 6- and 8-acylaminoquinolines have been prepared and their local anaesthetic properties studied. Similar compounds of 3-aminocarbazole have also been synthesised and are found to have potent anaesthetic efficiency as tested on rabbit's cornea.

In order to find out whether a simple amide grouping can act as an anchor for the production of local anaesthetic properties, some amides with a basic side-chain have been described (Part IV). It seemed that the extension of the principle to the quinoline series will result in the production of compounds of even more potent local anaesthetic activity. For this purpose, 6-aminoquinoline has been converted into chloroacyl derivatives (I) and these have been further interacted with diethylamine and piperidine.

The related products (piperidino-or diethylamino-acylaminoquinolines) with the side-chain at position 5 and 8, have also been prepared. The latter (side-chain at 8) have been found to have pronounced local anaesthetic activity, whilst the activity is much less in those compounds where the side-chain is attached at position 5 or 6.

The dihydrochloride of 3- ω -piperidinoacetylaminocarbazole (III) has been found to have very strong local anaesthetic properties.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Aminoquinoline was prepared essentially by the method of Knueppe (*Annalen*, 1900, **310**, 75), but the dark viscous product was extracted in a Soxhlet with ether and then recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 115° , yield 7 g. from 15 g. of 6-nitroquinoline.

6- ω -Chloroacetylaminocarbazole (I, $n=1$).—The foregoing aminoquinoline (5 g.) in benzene (30 c.c.) suspension was shaken with normal sodium carbonate solution in such a manner that the base accumulated at the

interface. Chloroacetyl chloride (1 mol.), dissolved in benzene, was made to run along the sides of the flask which was kept rotated. After standing for 2 hours, the mixture was thoroughly shaken, the solids collected and then crystallised from hot toluene in prisms, m.p. 154°. yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 13.30. $C_{11}H_9ON_2Cl$ requires N, 13.15 per cent). Alternatively the aminoquinoline (5 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) and a saturated solution of sodium acetate in water (20 c.c.), was treated with chloroacetyl chloride (2.7 c.c.) in the ice-cold. The product was precipitated with a large quantity of water and crystallised from hot toluene, yield 5 g.

6- ω -Piperidinoacetylaminquinoline (II, $n=1$, R replaced by piperidino).—The foregoing chloro compound (4.5 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.), was mixed with anhydrous sodium carbonate (1.6 g) and then refluxed after the addition of piperidine (2.5 g.) for 5 hours. The residue after the removal of alcohol from the filtered solution was well washed with water, dissolved in ether, dried, and then the solvent removed. Crystallised from hot petroleum ether (pointed rods), it had m.p. 101°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 15.61. $C_{16}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 15.40 per cent). The hydrochloride, prepared with ethereal hydrogen chloride in ether, crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether, m.p. 133°. (Found: Cl, 20.60. $C_{16}H_{19}ON_3, 2HCl$ requires Cl, 20.76 per cent).

Similarly *6- ω -diethylaminoacetylaminquinoline* was prepared with diethylamine in place of piperidine and was crystallised from petroleum ether in rectangular plates, m.p. 86°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 16.25. $C_{15}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent). The hydrochloride crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether, m.p. 250°. (Found: Cl, 21.80. $C_{15}H_{19}ON_3, 2HCl$ requires Cl, 21.4 per cent).

6- β -Chloropropionylaminquinoline was prepared in a manner analogous to the related chloroacetyl derivative and the product crystallised from dilute alcohol in prisms, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 11.98. $C_{12}H_{11}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 11.84 per cent).

6- β -Piperidinopropionylaminquinoline, prepared from the foregoing chloro compound in the manner described, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pentagonal plates, m.p. 67°. (Found: N, 14.86. $C_{17}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 15.17 per cent).

6- ω -Diethylaminopropionylaminquinoline, prepared as described before, was obtained as an oil. The base was converted into the dipicrate, m.p. 180° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 17.2. $C_{26}H_{27}O_{13}N_3$ requires N, 17.28 per cent).

The analogues of the foregoing compounds were prepared from 8- and 5-aminoquinolines by method essentially the same as described and the compounds are described in Table I.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Crystallised from.	M. p.	Analysis.	
			Found.	Calc.
8- ω -Chloroacetyl-aminoquinoline	33% Alcohol	131°	N, 12.56%	N, 12.72%
8- ω -Piperidinoacetyl-aminoquinoline hydrochloride	Dilute acetone.	77° (decomp.)	11.83	12.28
8- β -Chloropropionyl-aminoquinoline	Dilute alcohol	88°	11.76	11.94
8- β -Piperidinopropionyl-aminoquinoline	Petroleum ether	108°	14.37	14.84
The hydrochloride.	Alcohol-ether	189° (decomp.)	11.79	12.01
8- β -Diethylaminopropionyl-aminoquinoline dipicrate	Alcohol	167°	17.52	17.28
5- ω -Chloroacetyl-aminoquinoline hydrochloride (prepared in ethereal solution of the reactants)	Alcohol	157°	Cl, 27.48	Cl 27.62
5- ω -Piperidinoacetyl-aminoquinoline.	Water	62°	N, 15.86	N, 15.61
5- ω -Diethylaminoacetyl-aminoquinoline dipicrate	Alcohol	203°	17.48	17.63
5- β -Chloropropionyl-aminoquinoline hydrochloride (prepared in ether solution of reactants)	Alcohol	226° (decomp.)	10.13	10.33
Dipicrate of 5- β piperidinopropionyl-aminoquinoline.	Alcohol	230°	16.81	17.00
<i>Carbazole Series.</i>				
3- ω -Chloroacetyl-amino-carbazole	Dilute alcohol	203°	N, 10.78	N, 10.85
(a) 3- ω -Piperidinoacetylaminocarbazole.	Dilute alcohol	175°	13.52	13.68
Dihydrochloride of (a)	Alcohol-ether.	280°	Cl, 18.34	Cl, 18.68
(b) 3- ω -Diethylaminoacetylaminocarbazole	Dilute alcohol	99°	N, 14.51	N, 14.24
Dihydrochloride of (b)	Alcohol-ether.	232°	Cl, 19.02	Cl, 19.28
3- β -Chloropropionyl-amino-carbazole.	Alcohol	228° (decomp.)	N, 10.42	N, 10.20
(c) 1- β -Piperidinopropionylaminocarbazole	Benzene	219°	N, 14.86	N, 15.17
Dihydrochloride of (c)	Alcohol-ether.	298°	Cl, 17.78	Cl, 18.02

3-Aminocarbazole was prepared according to Perkin and Plant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1512).

The above substances were tested for local anaesthetic activity by the rabbit's cornea method and Table II shows the results.

TABLE II.

(The figures in parenthesis are for cocaine used as a standard).

	Time for onset of anaesthesia : complete loss of reflex action.	Duration for which complete loss of reflex action lasted.
Hydrochloride of 6- <i>o</i> -piperidinoacetylaminquinoline	Never complete (1-1/2 min)	Incomplete anaesthesia for 28 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride of 6- <i>o</i> -diethylaminoacetylquinoline	„ (1 min.)	Incomplete anaesthesia for 24 min. (37 min.)
Hydrochloride of 6- <i>β</i> -piperidinopropionylaminoquinoline	„ (1 min)	„ for 12 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride of 6- <i>β</i> -diethylaminopropionylaminoquinoline.	„ (1-1/2 min.)	„ for 10 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride of 8- <i>o</i> -piperidinoacetylaminquinoline	4 minutes (1 min.)	48 min. (35 min.)
Hydrochloride of 8- <i>β</i> -piperidinopropionylaminoquinoline	3 minutes (1 min.)	45 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride of 8- <i>β</i> -diethylaminopropionylaminoquinoline	4 minutes (1 min.)	44 min. (37 min)
Hydrochloride of 5- <i>o</i> - piperidinoacetylaminquinoline	Never complete (1 min.)	Incomplete lasting for 26 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride of 5- <i>o</i> -diethylaminoacetylaminquinoline	Never complete (1 min.)	„ for 24 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride 5- <i>β</i> -piperidinopropionylaminoquinoline	Never complete (1 min.)	Incomplete lasting for 23 min. (35 min.)
Hydrochloride of β-diethylaminopropionylaminoquinoline	Never complete (1 min.)	Incomplete lasting for 18 min. (36 min.)
Hydrochloride of 3- <i>o</i> -piperidinoacetylaminocarbazole	2 min. (1-1/2 min.)	94 min. (37 min.)
Hydrochloride of 3- <i>o</i> -diethylaminoacetylaminocarbazole	1-1/2 min. (1 min.)	86 min. (36 min.)

From the foregoing table it will appear that only 8-aminoquinoline derivatives possess local anaesthetic activity, whilst the related 5 or 6-amino quinolines do not show satisfactory results. The derivatives of 3-amino-carbazole cause profound local anaesthesia, approximately possessing about three times the potency of cocaine.

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